

The Influence of Delayed Flights on the Emotional Response and Behavioral Intention of Airline Passengers

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Abstract: *The study entitled, The Influence of Delayed Flights on Emotional Response and Behavioral Intention of Airline Passengers aimed to determine the relationship between the influence of delayed flights on airline passengers in terms of emotional response and behavioral intention from the 261 airline passengers in Francisco Bangoy International Airport, Davao City. The study used descriptive correlational research to determine the relationship between 2 variables from the same respondents. The researchers found out that the airline passengers in Francisco Bangoy International Airport, Davao City, showed a high emotional response and behavioral intention towards flight delays. There was a moderate positive relationship between emotional response and behavioral intention of airline passengers toward delayed flights. Furthermore, this study recommended that the Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines and the airline companies review the operating system and conduct training for the employees to improve the delivery of their services. Tourism Professors may include topics on airline passenger complaints, specifically in the Transportation Management subject and the Work Integrated Learning subject, to improve the handling of airline passengers.*

Keywords: Emotional Response, Behavioral Intention, Delayed Flights, Airline Passengers, Davao City

I. INTRODUCTION

Flight delay in real-time events is often considered the actual times compared to the scheduled times (National Academy of Sciences, 2014). Flight delays, missed connections, and cancellations are the reasons behind the distinction between great flight experiences and terrible experiences of travelers in the airline industry. Delayed and canceled flights on Christmas and the day after 2014 brought chaos at Ninoy Aquino International Airport (NAIA), Terminal 3. Instead of spending their holidays in their provinces, they cannot leave, which annoyed the passengers. By the 26th of noon, at least 14 complaints were reported to the Civil Aeronautics Board (CAB) counter at NAIA 3. One of the complainants was a foreigner from Israel who was told that he would be reassigned to another flight. According to the CAB personnel who witnessed the incident, the Israeli kept shouting at airline personnel, blaming Philippine authorities for their supposed inability. Tension ran high when more passengers were not processed on time for their flights. Another complainant said that the check-in counter was crowded and not in order. Cebu Pacific admitted that it was because of the insufficient workforce at the airport. The airline brought additional personnel from its service provider and asked others from its international check-in counters to assist passengers on domestic flights (Calleja, 2014).

Flight delays, or any case of waiting for service, can negatively influence customers from numerous points of view. Flight delays can expand passengers' outrage, uncertainty, and dissatisfaction with the service provided (Taylor, 1994). The U.S. airlines need to report the causes of their flight delays to the Department of Transportation every month. They must determine the cause among five reasons: maintenance or crew issues; late-arriving aircraft; aviation system delays; extreme weather; and security issues (Washington Post, 2013). It also includes fueling, air traffic congestion, baggage loading, and computer glitches (Medina, 2016).

The researchers aimed to determine the relationship between the emotional response and behavioral intention of the airline passengers affected by delayed flights. Also, this research will help the airline to be more knowledgeable and help them improve their airline service quality.

II. METHODS

1. Participants. The respondents of the study were 261 airline passengers in Davao City. The Normal Distribution decided the sample size from the sample size calculation of Raosoft.com. From the total number of airline passengers from April to May at Francisco Bangoy International Airport, 261 samples were derived. The research was conducted in July 2018 at Francisco Bangoy International Airport, Davao City.

2. Instrument. The study utilized an adapted two survey questionnaires that were adapted and modified from an analysis of the Impact of Airline Service Delays on Emotional Reactions and Customer Behavior by Kim and Park (2016) and Factors that Influence Customer Satisfaction and Behavioral Intentions in Airline Industry by Nonis et al. (2014). The first part was the profile of the respondent. The second part was about anger, uncertainty, and acceptability. The third part was about word-of-mouth communications, price sensitivity, purchase intention, and complaining behavior. It contained 18 statements that aimed to determine the influence of delayed flights on airline passengers' emotional responses and behavioral intention intentions.

3. Design and Procedure. The study used a descriptive correlational study, a quantitative method of research. According to Kalla (2011), a correlational study determines whether two variables are correlated. This means studying whether an increase or decrease in one variable corresponds to an increase or decrease in the other variable. According to Babbie and Mujis (2014), the quantitative method gathers numerical information. It generalizes it over groups of people to clarify a specific phenomenon, such as determining the relationship of the influence of delayed flights on emotional response and behavioral intention. The researchers investigated and collected data based on the respondents' answers through this method. The information acquired from survey questionnaires was utilized as the basis for judgment that may help in detailing the conclusion and recommendations of the researchers.

The researchers asked authorization from the Dean's office of the College Hospitality Education to conduct the study at Francisco Bangoy International Airport. After the approval of the questionnaire, it was personally distributed to the respondents and explained the purpose of the research and was automatically re-collected after answering. After gathering the data, the results were tallied and submitted to the statistician for further analysis and interpretation, which solved the problems stated in the research.

III. RESULTS

Table 1 shows that the airline passengers are highly affected in terms of their emotional response, with an overall mean of 3.73. This means the airline passengers feel angry and irritated when service delays occur; passengers feel uncertain and concerned because they do not know when will their delayed flights take off and agree that it is unavoidable to wait for airline service. They are willing to wait again to receive an airline service the next time they purchase.

Table 2 shows that airline passengers are highly affected by their behavioral intention, with an overall mean of 3.54. This means that airline passengers highly agreed that they would recommend and encourage friends, relatives, and other people to do business with the airline company; they will continue to do business with the airline that offers more attractive prices if they experience delayed flights, will switch to a competitor and complain to other consumers and external agencies if they encounter a problem with airline's service and will neither consider nor unconsidered the model of the airline as their first choice to buy.

Table 3 below shows that emotional response and behavioral intention have a moderate positive relationship with an R-value of 0.396. These results imply that behavioral intention such as word-of-mouth communication, purchase intention, price sensitivity, and complaining behavior is built when airline passengers experience negative emotions (anger, uncertainty, and acceptability) towards service delays, and negative emotions are developed while using the services of the airline company.

IV. FIGURES AND TABLES

Table 1. The Level of the Influence of Delayed Flights on Emotional Response of Airline Passengers in terms of Anger, Uncertainty, and Acceptability

Indicators	Mean(\bar{x})	Std. Deviation	Description
Anger	3.97	0.823	High
Uncertainty	3.77	0.664	High
Acceptability	3.44	0.663	High
Overall	3.73	0.717	High

Table 2. The Level of the Influence of Delayed Flights on Behavioral Intention of Airline Passengers in terms of Word-of-mouth Communication, Purchase Intention, Price Sensitivity, and Complaining Behavior

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
Word-of-Mouth Communication	3.35	0.814	High
Purchase Intention	3.29	0.799	Moderate
Price Sensitivity	3.71	0.760	High
Complaining Behavior	3.62	0.696	High
Overall	3.54	0.767	High

Table 4. Correlation between the Influence of Delayed Flights on Emotional Response and Behavioral Intention

Variables Correlated	r-value	Verbal Description	df (n-2)	p-value	Decision
Emotional Response vs Behavioral Intention	0.396**	Moderate Positive Relationship	259	0.000	Ho is rejected

Legend: **Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed)

V. DISCUSSION

Analysis of Emotional Response – In terms of anger was supported by Kim and Park (2016), who stated that service delay influenced the development of negative feelings, outrage, and vulnerability. In addition, Del Río-Lanza et al. (2009) noted that dissatisfaction could also affect the customers' emotional and behavioral responses to service failure. It focuses on the anger and actions of the customers, which occurs when an event is perceived as unpleasant or a block to goals or needs that reflect on what happened and make a thought-out judgment about how to act. Moreover, Bougie, Pieters, and Zeenlenberg (2003) stated that during the service failure, the passengers' anger is a significant indicator of consumer behavior than satisfaction.

In terms of uncertainty, airline passengers feel uncertain and worried as to when will their delayed flights take off because most of the airline companies here in the Philippines do not inform earlier the passengers if their flight is delayed, which is why most of the airline passengers feel uncertain as to when they will take off and will complain as to why they are not informed earlier. It was supported by the study results by Kim and Park (2016), which stated that uncertainty could not be said to have a significant influence on behavioral intention because the airline companies inform the passengers of the cause of the delay. On the other hand, Sarel and Marmorstein (1999) stated that the more the uncertainty, the more likely passengers would respond negatively to a service delay. Furthermore, uncertainty can negatively affect a consumer when a service failure occurs, and it causes them to wait for another time. Sometimes, the

service provider could not give assurance because they lacked confidence in their opinion and capabilities (Meijer et al., 2006).

In terms of acceptability, it was supported by Kim and Park (2016), who stated that it impacts repurchase intention and negative word-of-mouth. This means that the passengers are willing to wait and repurchase even if they experience service delays from the airline company. Hui and Tse (1996) and Taylor (1994) mentioned that waiting for delayed airline flights could result in negative emotions such as anger and uncertainty. In addition, waiting in service influenced the affective reaction and behavior of the consumers. Acceptability is the function of an amount that can be measured. The hostile service acquired, and service waits can cause by the time necessary for an airline flight when it is delayed (Baker & Cameron, 1996).

Analysis of Behavioral Intention - In terms of word-of-mouth, airline passengers highly agreed that they would involve themselves in spreading word-of-mouth to the people they know and trust because even they experience delays, they will still recommend the airline company considering the low-cost fares that most of the Filipinos are looking for in an airline company or full service that they are offering. It has been that the airline passengers will spread word-of-mouth on how much they are satisfied with the services being provided by the airline company to other people. It was supported by Park et al. (2014) and Yang et al. (2012) that service quality directly affects customers' behavioral intentions. The customers might use the same service and may tell other people how satisfied they are with the airline company's service quality. Additionally, Fisher, Garrett, Arnold, and Ferris (1999); Liu, Furrer, and Sudharshan (2001) mentioned that when the company meets the needs of the customers with the products and services that they are offering, the loyalty of the customer results to high positive reinforcement and other potential customers are encouraged to do business with the company.

Regarding purchase intention, the airline passengers considered or unconsidered purchasing services from the same airline company. It has been proven that the airline passengers will repurchase because of the benefits they can get from two different types of carriers (low-cost carriers and full-service carriers). Low-cost carriers offer low-cost fares and full-service carriers that provide complete services during the flight. It was supported by Maxham and Netemeyer (2002), who stated that satisfaction could keep word-of-mouth and purchase intention, which is most likely to repeat the purchase since the customer is pleased. Furthermore, Lin and Lekhawipat (2014) demonstrated that satisfied customers are expected to repurchase in the future than unsatisfied customers. Additionally, O'Connell and Williams (2005) stated that customers could still be happy with any type of carrier because customers who choose low-cost carriers are satisfied because of their low-cost fares, while the customers who decide on full-service carriers are confident because of the additional service quality that the airline company provides.

In terms of price sensitivity, the majority of the young Filipino professionals prefer low-cost fares to full-service carriers which offer expensive food despite experiencing flight delays from the same airline company. Some of them like the full-service packages that give them comfort and assurance. It has been seen in the studies that most of the customers that prefer cheaper flights serve it as just a mode of transportation. It was supported by Goldsmith et al. (2005), who mentioned that if the customer aims toward low value, they are price sensitive. In addition, based on the study results by Nonis et al. (2014), customers who travel for leisure purposes prefer to travel with low-cost carriers because it is cheaper and they just serve as transportation.

Furthermore, customers of low-cost airlines look at the airfares available first because they look for the lowest cost possible. Moreover, the study by O'Connell and Williams (2005) stated that low-cost fare is the primary factor in choosing low-cost carriers. Some passengers switch to other airline companies that offer more attractive prices and service quality.

In terms of complaining behavior, airline passengers who are negatively affected emotionally will most likely complain to other consumers or directly complain to the airline company regarding delays that may affect their schedules or plans for their trip to be compensated for their purchase. Wang (2017) mentioned that when a consumer experience a service failure, it will most likely influence the action of complaining and determine whether a complaint will be accommodated in that situation. Furthermore, Queensland Government (2016) stated that if the customers are dissatisfied with the company, they are uncomfortable complaining directly to the company. They will most likely complain first to others before complaining to the company. Moreover, Zeithaml et al. (2013) noted that customers who do not complain simply switch to another company and have a small percentage to purchase again.

Significant Relationship between Emotional Response and Behavioral Intention - The behavioral intention is built

when airline passengers experience negative emotions towards service delays, and negative emotions are developed while using the services of the airline company. Bedi supported the result of the study (2010), Maiyaki and Mokhtar (2011), and Urich (2011), which stated that consumer behavioral reaction has risen as a key to measuring the level of consumer loyalty, recommendation, and responsibility toward the service provider. Thus, the behavioral response is influenced by the person's condition of feelings built during service consumption. Moreover, Lawler and Yoon (2012) stated that when service failure happens, passengers encounter negative emotions and react negatively to the relationship leading to discouraging responses toward service providers. Thus, the injustice experienced by passengers during a service experience may result in an emotional response that impacts their behavioral intentions. In addition, Baig et al. (2014) cited that emotion is the most common social mentality phenomenon. The changes in emotions reflect the behavioral modifications that bring behaviors in different situations.

VI. CONCLUSION

The Theory of Planned Behavior explains how airline passengers make logical and reasoned decisions to engage in such behavior by assessing available information (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1985). Furthermore, behavioral intention predicts whether a customer will continue to consume a company's services or not continue to do business with the company and switch to competitors (Zeithaml and Bitner, 1996).

Therefore, the researchers conclude that there is a significant relationship between the influence of delayed flights on emotional response and behavioral intention of airline passengers, which means that behavioral intention is built when airline passengers experience negative emotions towards service delays. Negative emotions are developed while using the services of the airline company. The researchers wanted to extend information about the relationship between the influence of delayed flights on emotional responses and the behavioral intention of airline passengers. This vital information is significant to encourage reviewing the operating system, conducting training for the employees, and improving the airline service quality.

REFERENCES

- [1] Adeleke, A., & Suraju, A. A. (2012). The determinants of customer loyalty in Nigeria's GSM market. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(14).
- [2] Ajzen, I. (1985). From intention to actions: A theory of planned behavior. In Kuhl, J., & Beckmann, J. (Eds.), *Action control: From cognition to behavior*, pp. 11-39. Berlin: Springer-Verlag.
- [3] Babbie, E. R., & Muijs, D. (2011). *Doing Quantitative Research in Education with SPSS*. doi:10.4135/9781849203241
- [4] Baig M. W., Barakova, E. I., Marcenaro, L., Rauterberg, M., & Regazzoni, C. S. (2014). Crowd emotion detection using dynamic probabilistic models. *The International Conference on the Simulation of Adaptive Behavior*, Vol. 56, pp. 842-842.
- [5] Baker, J., & Cameron, M. (1996). The effects of the service environment on affect and consumer perception of waiting time: An integrative review and research propositions. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Service*, 24, pp. 338-349.
- [6] Baksi, A. K. & Parida, B. B. (2013). An empirical study to link CRM initiatives with service quality perception, tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty. *International Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Systems*, 6(2). Retrieved July 30, 2018, from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1733224803?accountid=31259>
- [7] Balter, D., & Butman, J. (2005). Grapevine: The new art of word-of-mouth marketing. *Publishers Weekly*, 252(37), pp. 56-57.
- [8] Bansal, H. S., & Voyer, P. A. (2000). Word-of-mouth processes within a services purchase decision context. *Journal of Service Research*, 3(2), pp. 166-177.

- [9] Bedi M. (2010). An Integrated Framework for Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction and Behavioural Responses in Indian Banking Industry: A Comparison of Public and Private Sector Banks. *Journal of Service Research*, Vol. 10, No. 1, pp. 157-172.
- [10] Black, K. (2010). *Business Statistics: Contemporary Decision Making*, 6th Edition. Retrieved July 7, 2018, from https://research-methodology.net/sampling_inprimary-data-collection/purposive-sampling/
- [11] Bougie, R., Pieters, R., &Zeelenberg, M. (2003). Angry customers don't come back, they get back: The experience and behavioral implications of anger and dissatisfaction in services. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 31(4), pp. 377-393.
- [12] Calleja, N. P. (2014). Chaos, flight delays hound NAlA. *Philippine Daily Inquirer*. Retrieved September 3, 2018, from <http://newsinfo.inquirer.net/659642/naia-3-turns-out-to-be-gateway-to-nowhere-for-many>
- [13] Casado Diaz, A. B., & Mas Ruiz, F. J. (2002). The consumer's reaction to delays inservice. *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, 13(2), pp. 118-140. Retrieved August 13, 2018, from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/233468590?accountid=31259>
- [14] Cho, Y. C. (2013). Exploring relationship among customer dissatisfaction, complaints, and loyalty in the virtualized environment: Roles of advanced services. *The International Business & Economics Research Journal (Online)*, 12(11), pp. 1343-n/a. Retrieved September 22, 2018 from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1458944611?accountid=3125>
- [15] Choraria, S. (2013). Exploring the role of negative emotions on customer's intention to complain. *Vision*, 17(3), pp. 201-211. Retrieved August 13, 2018, from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1503058899?accountid=31259>
- [16] Committee on Communication for Behavior Change in the 21st Century (2002). Behavioral intention definition. *Consumer Health Informatics Research Resource*. Retrieved October 23, 2018, from <https://chirr.nlm.nih.gov/behavioral-intention.php>
- [17] Corrada, M.D.L.M.S, Varela, J.C.S., &Svensson, G. (2015). Customers service experience in hospitals: A Dip and SOS construct of negative encounters. In Robinson, Jr., Leroy (Ed.), *Marketing dynamism & sustainability: Things change, things stay the same*, pp. 283-289. New Orleans, Louisiana: Springer International Publishing.
- [18] Del Río-Lanza, A. B., Vázquez-Casielles, R., & Díaz-Martín, A. M. (2009). Satisfaction with service recovery: Perceived justice and emotional responses. *Journal of Business Research*, 62(8), pp. 775-781. Retrieved September 06, 2018, from <http://hamkarfile.ir/up/974.pdf>
- [19] Ding, Y. (2017). Predicting flight delay based on multiple linear regression. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science, Vol. 81, No. 1, p. 012198). IOP Publishing. Retrieved June 27, 2018, from <http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1755-1315/81/1/012198/pdf>
- [20] Erkmen, E., Hancer, M. (2015). Linking brand commitment and brand citizenship behaviors of airline employees: The role of trust. *J. Air Transp. Manag.* 42, pp. 47-54.
- [21] Fishbein, M., & Ajzen, I. (1975). *Beliefs, attitudes, intention and behavior: An introduction to theory and research*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
- [22] Fisher, J. E., Garrett, D. E., Arnold, M. J., & Ferris, M. E. (1999). Dissatisfied consumers who complain to the Better Business Bureau. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, Vol. 16 Issue: 6, pp. 576-589. Retrieved July 14, 2018, from <https://doi.org/10.1108/07363769910297515>
- [23] Folkes, V. S., Koletsky, S., & Graham, J. L. (1987). A field study of causal inferences and consumer reaction: The view from the airport. *Journal of Consumer Research*, Vol. 13, pp. 534-539.
- [14] Friman, M. (2010). Affective Dimensions of the Waiting Experience, *Transportation Research. Part F, Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, Vol.13 No.3, 97-205.

- [15] Frow, P., & Payne A. (2014). A strategic framework for customer relationship management. *Journal of Marketing*. Vol. 69, No. 4, pp. 167-176.
- [16] Godes, D., & Mayzlin, D. (2009). Firm-created word-of-mouth communication: Evidence from a field test. *Marketing Science*, 28(4), pp. 721-739.
- [17] Goldsmith, R. E., Kim, D., Flynn, L. R., & Kim, W. M. (2005). Price sensitivity and Innovativeness for fashion among Korean consumers. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 145 (5), pp. 501-508.
- [18] Han, H., & Hwang, J. (2015). Quality of physical surroundings and service encounters, airfare, trust and intention during the flight. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 27(4), pp. 585-607. Retrieved September 22, 2018, from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-08-2013-0344>
- [19] Hellier et al. (2003). Customer repurchase intention: A general structural equation model. *European Journal of Marketing*. Vol. 37, No. 11/12, pp. 1762-1800.
- [20] Hui, M. K., & Tse, D. K. (1996). What to tell consumers in waits of different lengths: An integrative model of service evaluation. *Journal of Marketing*, 60, pp. 81-90.
- [21] Influence [Def. 1]. (n.d.). In *English Oxford Living Dictionaries*. Retrieved October 23, 2018 from <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/influence>
- [22] Kalla, S. (2011). Correlational Study. Retrieved Nov 03, 2018 from *Explorable.com*: <https://explorable.com/correlational-study>
- [23] Kaur P., & Sharma S. K. (2015). A Measure of Consumer Complaining Behaviour in Service Industry: Scale Validation. Retrieved September 21, 2018, from <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0971890715585200#articleCitationDownloadContainer>
- [24] Kim Y. S., & Park J. W. (2017). A Study on the Impact of Online Word-of-Mouth for Airlines on Customer Behavior. Retrieved August 13, 2018, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320168991_A_Study_on_theImpact_of_Online_Word-of-Mouth_for_Airlines_on_Customer_Behavior
- [25] Kim, I., & Cho, M. (2014). The impact of brand relationship and attributions on passenger response to service failure. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 19(12), pp. 1441-1462. Retrieved August 10, 2018, from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10941665.2013.866582>
- [26] Kim, N.Y., & Park, J.W. (2016). A study on the impact of airline service delays on emotional reactions and customer behavior. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, Vol. 57, pp. 19-25.